

Exploring the regional changes in the structure of student mobility in Europe: before and after Covid-19

Tuomas Väisänen^{1,*}, Milad Malekzadeh¹, Oula Inkeröinen^{1,2}, and Olle Järv¹

¹Digital Geography Lab, University of Helsinki

²Statistics Finland

Abstract Student mobility represents the temporary migration of highly-skilled individuals and serves as an indicator of regional attractiveness from academic and economic perspectives. Understanding its spatio-temporal distribution can provide essential insights for regional planning, policy, and governance. This study examines how the structure of Erasmus+ student mobility has evolved post-Covid-19, using spatially enriched data from 2014 to 2022, encompassing over 2 million participants. Through cluster and statistical analyses, we investigate hierarchical and regional changes in Erasmus+ mobility and present methods to visualize complex origin-destination data. Our findings highlight shifts in student mobility across NUTS 3 regions and countries, revealing evolving regional brain gain and drain dynamics, with significant implications for regional and educational planning and policies at both national and international levels.

1 Introduction

Mobility of people reveals how regions are connected to each other, how societies function, and how these connections and functions change over time. Consequently, mobility can be seen as a tool with which to understand society and provide new insights (Kaufmann, 2014) on cross-border social interactions (Järv et al., 2023; Setti, 2024), and how urban mobility structures and socio-economic inequalities changed due to Covid-19 (Müürisepp, 2023; Rowe et al., 2023; Schmahmann et al., 2022). Student mobility is a form of mobility that can be seen as a relevant indicator of the attractiveness and performance of localities from the economic and innovation perspectives. The mobility of students is one of the cornerstones in the dissemination of academic knowledge and fostering international networks of expertise (Breznik & Skrbinjek, 2019; Cuzzocrea & Krzaklewska, 2023; Earls, 2018), and thus, can create a regional hierarchy of brain gain and brain drain regions (Gérard & Sanna, 2017; Rasamoelison et al., 2021; Wende, 2015).

* Correspondence to tuomas.vaisanen@helsinki.fi

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The Erasmus+ programme of the European Union is among the largest student mobility networks globally. It has supported the mobility of 16 million students since 1987 (Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, 2024b) and has an important role in fostering a shared European identity for students in the EU member, partner, and candidate nations (Breznik & Skrbinjek, 2019; Croce & Ghignoni, 2024; Oborune, 2013). As a result of Covid-19, the international mobility of Erasmus+ students reduced drastically, however it has started to quickly recover. Yet, it is not known how the pandemic has affected the regional structure and hierarchy of student mobility in Europe.

In this work, we analyse regional changes in Erasmus+ student mobility across Europe from 2014 until 2022 using a spatially enriched version of Erasmus+ student mobility data at NUTS 3 (Nomenclature for Statistical Territorial Unit) spatial level (Väisänen et al., 2025). The data are based on the open student mobility statistics provided by the European Union (Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, 2024a) and have been spatially enriched by geocoding the origins and destinations in the individual-level mobility data.

2 Data and methods

2.1 Erasmus+ data

The spatially enriched Erasmus+ data contains student mobilities on the NUTS 3 regional level on an annual basis from 2014 until 2022 (Väisänen et al., 2025). The data contains the student mobilities of 2 282 950 participants of the Erasmus+ programme who are at least 18 years old students whose mobility has lasted for at least 90 days. The data is openly available from Väisänen et al. (2025).

2.2 Methods

We assess the changing patterns of regional student mobility by performing K-means clustering using dynamic time warping. Dynamic time warping is a specific metric developed for clustering time series data that can deal with the specific challenges arising from clustering time series data (Petitjean et al., 2011). We perform these analyses on net mobility values of the mobility flows and on the diversity of received mobilities. Finally, we explore how to visualize complex mobility flow data using an edge bundling technique, namely edge-path bundling (Wallerger et al., 2022). Edge bundling is a visualisation technique where existing line geometries going to a similar direction get bundled together to reduce visual clutter and to support a better legibility of complex flow data. This technique does not add any

new information to the data, just alters the geometries of the line geometry features. Specifically, we used our own edge bundling tool (Väisänen et al., 2024).

3 Results and discussion

3.1 General mobility trends and structure

Erasmus+ student mobility has been consistently on the rise throughout the years (Figure 1), and has started to rebound after the Covid-19 shock. The abrupt shock of the pandemic and other geopolitical changes in Europe such as Brexit and Russia’s invasion of Ukraine have likely altered the regional distribution of student mobility.

Fig. 1 Total counts of Erasmus+ student mobility from 2014 to 2022. The influence of Covid-19 is clearly visible.

The structure of the flow network has undergone considerable changes after the Covid-19 pandemic (Figure 2). The pre-Covid-19 (2014–2019) mobility flow structure (Figure 2a) shows major European cities (Paris, London, Berlin, Madrid, Barcelona, Rome etc.) forming the linchpins of the student mobility network with other regions having a lesser role. In contrast, the post-Covid-19 (2020–2022) flow structure (Figure 2b) shows extensive diversification of regions in the most dominant flows. While the pre-Covid-19 flow structure between major cities in Europe is still present after 2020, the flow structure has expanded to regions in Northern and Eastern Europe specifically. These are very likely results of the Covid-19 pandemic and Brexit altering the pool of possible and desirable destinations for students.

Fig. 2 Edge-bundled Erasmus+ student mobility flows (a.) before Covid-19, and (b.) after Covid-19 on the NUTS 3 level.

3.2 Cluster analysis

We performed K-Means clustering analysis with dynamic time warping on the net mobility per each NUTS 3 region and country to find clusters of regions with similar mobility efficiency profile. Mobility efficiency describes the mobility balance of the spatial unit. Its values range between 1 and -1, with 1 indicating the region is only receiving students, -1 indicating the region is only sending students, and 0 indicating a balance between sent and received students. We tried multiple numbers of clusters to find the optimal number: based on the Elbow method and Silhouettes scores, the optimal number is four clusters.

Table 1 provides basic characteristics of the four clusters on NUTS 3 and country levels including a general description of the cluster by the authors. Silhouette scores indicate the clusters on NUTS 3 level are have low stability, and on the country level the clusters are more stable. Nonetheless, the clusters capture different types of regions in terms of student mobility: consistent net receivers and senders, but also some regions and countries undergoing changes (see also Figure 3).

Table 1 Clustering results on the NUTS 3 and country-level.

Clusters		NUTS 3		Country	
Cluster	Description	Silhouette	Count	Silhouette	Count
0	Stable net receiver	0.252	278	0.528	15
1	Stable net sender	0.283	316	0.600	10
2	Major net receiver	0.370	119	0.119	6
3	Major net sender	0.393	146	0.186	3

The stable clusters on the NUTS 3 level have the most members (Table 1), and most changes are occurring in regions that are considered net receivers (Figure 3a).

In the country perspective, six countries are becoming a major net receiver according to the cluster analysis (Figure 3b). Luxembourg, Liechtenstein, Iceland, Norway, Sweden, and Malta are attracting increasingly more students, while the amount of students leaving the countries has been reducing. Conversely, Turkey, and most countries in the Balkans are increasingly sending more students than they are receiving, however this appears to be changing post-Covid-19 (Figure 3b).

Fig. 3 Mobility efficiency between NUTS 3 regions and countries participating in the Erasmus+ programme. Positive values describe regions/countries that are receiving more students than they are sending, whereas negative values describe those who are sending more than they are receiving. The colours represent the four clusters and the confidence intervals represent 95 % confidence.

Fig. 4 Clusters identified on (a.) the NUTS 3 level and on (b.) the country-level cluster analysis on a map. The colors for clusters represent the same clusters as in Figure 3.

Figure 4 shows the distribution of the across Europe on NUTS 3 level (a.) and on the country-level (b.). Most of northern Europe are net receivers in both perspectives, whereas many regions and countries in the Balkans and Eastern Europe are rather consistent senders in both perspectives. More regional variation appears elsewhere in Europe. Larger cities are consistent major net receivers, whereas smaller cities and more peripheral regions tend to vary between being a stable net receiver and a stable net sender (Figure 4a). Countries that are separated from mainland Europe by maritime areas, such as the Nordics, Ireland, the UK and Cyprus alongside with Portugal, appear to be steadily receiving more students than they are sending (Figure 4b).

3.3 Considerations

The analysis and associated data presented here come with some considerations. First, the geocoded Erasmus+ data by Väisänen et al. (2025) used in this work contains only student mobilities enabled by the Erasmus+ programme. Student mobility enabled by other mobility programmes like Nordplus, Fulbright, and bilateral agreements between institutions are not included in this data. Second, Brexit effectively ended Erasmus+ mobility between the UK and rest of participating countries, although Erasmus+ mobility projects funded before Brexit will run their course normally (Finnish National Agency for Education, 2024; United Kingdom Government, 2022). Third, the geocoded data might contain some errors with similar place names from the same country, with more prominent locations being preferred. However, this aspect will likely be a minor one. For more detailed description regarding the considerations on using the data, please see the Data Descriptor article by Väisänen et al. (2025). Finally, the Silhouette scores of the clusters presented here are fairly low (Table 1), indicating the clusters are not very stable and potentially other approaches would be better-suited for extracting more robust information from the student mobility. Regardless, the results presented here provide an introductory understanding on how Erasmus+ student mobility has developed regionally in Europe in the past ten years.

3.4 Conclusions

Erasmus+ student mobility has undergone changes in Europe during the last ten years. During the study period major world events, such as Brexit and the Covid-19 pandemic affected the student mobilities in Europe on a regional level. Long-standingly popular regions with major global cities have remained popular destinations, however more remote regions have started to attract students as well. Countries and regions in the Balkans and along the Black Sea coast seem to struggle in attracting students. More research is needed to understand what are driving these

developments. While a third major geopolitical event, Russia's invasion of Ukraine in February 2022, occurred during the data, this is not visible in the data. Potentially newer data, containing the subsequent academic years of 2022–2023 and 2023–2024 would reveal the impact of the largest war in Europe in 80 years on student mobility.

Student mobility provides a valuable, and an underexamined perspective to understanding regional attractiveness and performance. Many regional analyses that are only based on one type of mobility, very commonly permanent migration, leave several important aspects of regional integration and economics unexplored. Student mobility can provide new perspectives by providing insights on what regional characteristics attract students, which push them away, and how regional planning and policymaking can leverage this information to improve their region's performance.

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